

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING AS AN INNOVATION APPROACH OF THE 21ST CENTURY

Bozorova Zulhumor Jurayevna

Surkhandarya region legal technical school, English teacher

<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7783692>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 22th March 2023

Accepted: 29th March 2023

Online: 30th March 2023

KEY WORDS

Project-based education, pedagogical tool, innovative and practical approach, successful projects, project methods.

ABSTRACT

The article demonstrates that Project-Based Learning is an innovative, hands-on approach to creating meaningful learning experiences for 21st century students.

Project-based learning, which is often discussed together with inquiry-based learning or problem-based learning, is very popular and highly recommended for English language teachers. It is becoming an effective pedagogical tool. Although it involves more than just creating a project, PBL is used in a variety of educational settings. Most teachers prefer to use PBL as a hands-on approach to engage their students in critical thinking and learning new content. How is PBL different from a basic thematic unit plan? Although the general purpose of PBL is to integrate several topics into a single project, it is not simply a collection of lessons on a single topic, but a type of learning that culminates in a project. There are some specific ways in which it differs from other learning styles:

- Project work is meaningful and serves as a pulpit for lessons;
- Development and creation of projects arise from students' interests or problems;
- The teacher's role is not to do a lot of direct teaching, but to guide the students through the project; The project implementation process must be in the classroom, last many months, connect with other educational institutions, or affect the community;
- Although students can complete individual assignments, emphasis is placed on cooperative and collaborative learning;
- Students interact with the project every day, and lessons are added to the project;
- The project is done by students in class. There will be no intervention of the teacher or parents;
- At the end of the project, students are given enough time to reflect and share their experiences.

Examples of successful projects

The term project-based learning is used in many ways, and educators have different ideas about what exactly constitutes a project. One of the most common projects is topics that

focus the class on finding a solution to a specific problem in the world. We do this in English lessons on the topic "Save the...". That is, there can be topics such as "Save the water", "Save the world" or "Save the nature". Here are some easily modifiable projects that incorporate a constructivist approach to learning new content:

Weather Station!(Weather Station!) Create and save two (or more) weather stations on your site. Send the second to another site. Have each student be a meteorologist for a day, where they record the weather for the day. Collect data over several weeks. Then compare the data to your own sites and help young scientists make discoveries about how the weather changes from day to day and over time. Teach data collection such as earth science standards, graphs, and data collection standards

'Make sure you integrate lessons focused on specific academic standards by engaging in hands-on writing activities, reading relevant literature, and conducting class discussions.

Planning a culminating activity. Such opportunities include a rotation day across different educational institutions or inviting parents to participate in a project. Summarizing all the points presented in our article, we can conclude that Project-based education (PBL) is truly a proof of positive practical results as an innovative approach of the 21st century. During the implementation of projects, today's student receives real independent education and engages in independent research. The most important thing is that the student can develop his self-confidence and creativity while discovering his undiscovered and unrealized abilities. This indicates that today's 21st century education system has begun to achieve its goals.

References:

1. Agustina, L. (2012). Project-based education. Journal Linguistic Therapy. October 31, 2014.
2. Jamal Jalolov (2012) Methodology of external teaching. - T.: Teacher. 3rd p
3. What Is Project Based Learning (PBL)?, www.bie.org/about/what_pbl. Accessed 10 Mar. 2018